

The Formation of the Sodium Derivatives of Compounds Containing a Reactive Methylene Group.

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It is well-known that the hydrogen atoms in groupings such as

are replaceable by sodium, and that the property depends upon the accumulation of residual affinity in the immediate neighbourhood of the replaceable hydrogen. Bland and Thrope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 874) have advocated that the stability of the sodium compounds of the various glutaconic esters must be dependent upon the acid character of the displaced hydrogen, the acidity being determined by the nature of the groups attached to the carbon atom which carries the hydrogen atom and they further hold that in those cases in which one carbethoxy group is attached to the carbon atom, the sodium compound is completely dissociated by water. It is also known that ethyl cyanoacetate and cyanoacetamide give mono-sodium derivatives (Henry, *Compt. rend.*, 1887, 104, 1619; Hesse, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1896, 18, 724). The present work was therefore undertaken to study the relationship which may exist between the acid character of the hydrogen atom of a reactive methylene group and the formation of its sodium derivative by the replacement of such a hydrogen. The following substances were examined:

(1) Cyanacet-*m*-toluidide, (2) cyanacet-*o*-toluidide, (3) cyanacet-*p*-toluidide, (4) cyanacetbenzylamide, (5) cyanacet- α -naphthylamide, (6) cyanacet- β -naphthylamide, (7) cyanacetmethylamide, (8) cyanacetbutylamide and (9) cyanacetheptylamide.

All the substances enumerated above react with metallic sodium in presence of dry benzene or anhydrous ether, yielding products having the general formula, $\text{CN}\cdot\text{CHNa}\cdot\text{COR}$ ($\text{R}=\text{OEt}$, NH_2 , NHMe , etc.).

The above general constitution has been assigned to the compounds from the following considerations:

(1) That the sodium atom has not replaced the hydrogen atom of the nucleus, for, cyanacetmethylamide which does not contain such a nucleus forms a similar mono-sodium derivative.

(2) That the sodium atom has not entered the aliphatic part of the amido group, for, cyanoacetamide which does not contain such an aliphatic part, forms a similar mono-substitution product with metallic sodium (Hesse, *loc. cit.*).

(3) That the sodium atom has not replaced the hydrogen attached to the nitrogen atom of the $-NH\cdot R$ group for,

(a) Ethyl cyanoacetate, which does not contain such a hydrogen forms a similar mono-substituted product with metallic sodium (Henry, *loc. cit.*).

Sidgwick and Brewer (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2379) have shown that the alkaline derivatives of β -diketones, β -ketonic esters, *o*-hydroxy aromatic esters and aldehydes and *o*-nitrophenols behave in one of the three ways as exemplified below:

(I) The sodium derivative of ethyl malonate is insoluble in benzene and chars without melting: it behaves as a salt.

(II) The sodium derivative of ethyl methylmalonate dissolves in benzene to form a clear solution from which the compound does not separate immediately even on concentration; but once it has separated, it is quite insoluble in benzene or toluene.

(III) The sodium derivative of ethyl acetoacetate is soluble in hot toluene and melts to a clear liquid at 108° .

The compounds obtained during the present course of the work must be classed as salts of type I given above, since they are insoluble in benzene and toluene and do not give definite melting points.

During the course of their investigations on the factors governing the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of a reactive methylene group situated between two negative groups as in the case of compounds containing the groupings

it has been observed by Naik and his collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379; 1922, 121, 2592, etc.) that the reactivity increases in direct proportion to the increase in the negativity of the carbonyl group with its attached groupings; so that in a series like—

the reactivity increases from (1) to (6).

The experiments described herein afford clear evidence that the interaction of metallic sodium with compounds containing the methylene radicle, depends on the electronegative character of the attached groups. Thus, ethyl cyanoacetate reacts with metallic sodium with the greatest rapidity forming the monosubstitution product even in the cold, while cyanacet-*m*-toluidide requires about six hours' heating in benzene solution. In the case of cyanacet-*a*-naphthylamide the reaction is found to be still slower.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sodiocyanacet-m-toluidide.—To a flask containing molecular sodium (0.3 g.) (prepared by heating under boiling toluene in the usual way) about 30 c.c. of anhydrous benzene were added, followed by cyanacet-*m*-toluidide (2 g.). The flask was heated under reflux when the amide went into solution. After about half an hour, a white gelatinous mass began to separate. The heating was continued for six hours and the mixture filtered hot. The solid obtained was washed with hot benzene several times and then with light petroleum (b. p. 50-60°). It was then dried in a desiccator over sulphuric acid.

The product was a white amorphous mass insoluble in most of the ordinary organic solvents such as benzene, toluene, ether and petroleum. It charred at 230° but did not melt even up to 300°. Even when preserved in a sealed tube, the product turned pink. (Found: Na, 11.88 ; N, 13.89. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2\text{Na}$ requires Na, 11.73 ; N, 14.28 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid.—About 0.5 g. of the above substance was treated with 5 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The substance underwent decomposition which was evident from the profound frothing that took place. Water was then added to the mixture and the solid was washed several times with cold water. It was then crystallised from benzene and identified as pure cyanacet-*m*-toluidide, m.p. 132°.

Action of Water.—0.124 G. of the above substance suspended in water was heated for about half an hour. The liberated alkali was titrated against 0.051N-hydrochloric acid of which 12.6 c.c.

were required. This showed the presence of 1.02 equivalents of alkali indicating that the decomposition was quantitative.

Sodiocyanacet-o-toluidide was prepared as in the above case. It has no definite melting point but turned deep red above 190° and blackened at 220° without melting. (Found: Na, 11.94; N, 14.45. $C_{10}H_9ON_2Na$ requires Na, 11.73; N, 14.28 per cent.).

Sodiocyanacet-p-toluidide.—The reaction was found to be much slower in this case and took nearly twelve hours for completion. The compound turned deep red above 245° and then blackened without melting to a clear liquid. (Found: Na, 11.58. $C_{10}H_9ON_2Na$ requires Na, 11.73 per cent.).

Sodiocyanacetbenzylamide was prepared from cyanacetbenzylamide (2 g.) and metallic sodium. It changed its colour from white to pink. It was insoluble in benzene and toluene and blackened at 205° without melting. (Found: Na, 12.05. $C_{10}H_9ON_2Na$ requires Na, 11.73 per cent.).

Sodiocyanacet- α -naphthylamide was prepared from cyanacet- α -naphthylamide (2 g.) and metallic sodium (0.3 g.) in presence of anhydrous benzene. The heating had to be continued for twelve hours. The compound turned deep red above 170° and at high temperatures fused to a dark mass without melting. (Found: Na, 9.82. $C_{13}H_9ON_2Na$ requires Na, 9.91 per cent.).

Sodiocyanacet- β -naphthylamide was prepared as in the above case from cyanacet- β -naphthylamide and metallic sodium. It turned brown above 205° but did not melt even up to 300°. (Found: Na, 9.78. $C_{13}H_9ON_2Na$ requires Na, 9.91 per cent.).

Sodiocyanacetmethylamide.—In the case of the alkyl amides of cyanoacetic acid, ether was used as the solvent.

Cyanacetmethylamide (2 g.) was put in a flask and covered with about 25 c.c. of dry ether distilled over sodium. Finely divided sodium (0.4 g.) which had been purified by boiling under toluene, was then added. A calcium chloride tube was attached to the flask. At the end of two days the precipitated solid was taken out and extracted with small portions of hot benzene and finally washed with light petroleum. On drying in a desiccator over sulphuric acid, the product assumed a pink colour. It turned deep red above 190° and melted with decomposition at 225°. (Found: Na, 19.42. $C_4H_5ON_2Na$ requires Na, 19.17 per cent.).

Sodiocyanacetbutylamide was prepared as in the preceding case. The reaction was found to be much rapid in this case. The product

melted with decomposition at 200° . (Found: Na, 14.03; N, 17.37. $C_7H_{11}ON_2Na$ requires Na, 14.20; N, 17.28 per cent.).

Sodiocyanacetheptylamide.—This was prepared as in the preceding cases by the action of metallic sodium on cyanacetheptylamide in presence of anhydrous ether. A red solid was obtained which was repeatedly extracted with hot benzene and finally washed with light petroleum. It melted with decomposition at 195° . (Found: Na, 11.39. $C_{10}H_{17}ON_2Na$ requires Na, 11.27 per cent.).

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